

Research Article

Volume Approximation of Mount Kinabalu: A Goursat Problem-Based Prototype Simulator

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Abstract: This innovation introduces a groundbreaking approach to geographical modeling by applying the Goursat problem to represent Mount Kinabalu's surface. Utilizing the forward difference method, the study approximates the mountain's volume with enhanced precision through numerical analysis techniques. This innovative framework not only estimates the volume of Mount Kinabalu but also revolutionizes the application of the Goursat problem to complex geographical features. By providing a more precise terrain representation, this methodology significantly benefits fields such as environmental science, urban planning, and landscape management. A key outcome of this research is the development of a prototype simulator, equipped with user-friendly interfaces and robust algorithms, facilitating precise terrain analysis and volume estimation. This simulator, adaptable for other geographical regions, enhances accessibility for researchers, educators, and practitioners in geography. Additionally, it promotes interdisciplinary collaboration, offering a common platform for professionals in mathematics, environmental science, and engineering to analyze geographical data. Overall, this innovation marks a significant advancement in applying advanced mathematical concepts to real-world geographical challenges, showcasing the transformative potential of the Goursat problem in understanding and interacting with natural environments.

Keywords: Goursat problem, forward difference method, Mont Kinabalu, volume estimation, prototype simulator.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The basic form of the Goursat partial differential equation problem is as follows (Nasir & Md Ismail, 2013):

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_{xy} &= f(x, y, u, u_x, u_y) \\
 u(x, 0) &= g(x), \quad u(0, y) = m(y) \\
 g(0) &= m(0) = u(0, 0) \\
 0 \leq x &\leq a, \quad 0 \leq y \leq b.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{1}$$

where u_{xy} is the mixed derivative in space x and y and $f(x, y, u, u_x, u_y)$ is a function of the two independent variables x and y , the dependent variable u and the derivative terms u_x and u_y .

A variety of innovative techniques have been proposed to tackle the Goursat problem, Newton-Cotes Integration (Deraman & Nasir, 2015), reduction differential transform (Naseem, 2022), the fuzzy transform (Saharizan & Zamri, 2019), iterative regularization (Meziani et al., 2021), Signature Kernel (Salvi et al., 2021) and method of transmutation operators (Sitnik & Karimov, 2023). Enhancing the comprehension and refining these methods will significantly improve the mathematical modeling of related problems. This study specifically targets the use of the forward difference method to approximate the left-hand side of the Goursat problem.

Applying the Goursat problem to real-life scenarios presents challenges, particularly because of its specific form. The complexities in accurately representing geographical features often impede practical implementation. Thus, by reworking any surface equation in terms of u_{xy} , it becomes much easier to convert various applications into the Goursat problem form. For instance, reformulating the surface equation of Mount Kinabalu to align with the Goursat problem allows for the use of advanced mathematical techniques to estimate surface regions and volumes. This method effectively bridges the gap between theoretical mathematics and real-world geographical analysis, promising significant advancements in research and applications across multiple disciplines.

Additionally, developing a prototype simulator specifically for calculating mountain volumes allows users to effortlessly obtain estimated results via a user-friendly interface. This tool acts as an accessible resource for both researchers and practitioners, facilitating calculations without requiring extensive mathematical expertise. Its intuitive design lets users input surface equations and receive instant estimations, thereby simplifying the terrain analysis process.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The methodology is divided into five key steps, as shown in the flowchart in Figure 1. It begins with the extraction of the surface equation, which involves gathering data from various sources to construct Mount Kinabalu's surface equation. This is followed by the formulation of the Goursat problem, which involves converting the derived equation into Goursat problem format and specifying the initial value conditions. The numerical method is then implemented by using the forward difference method to solve the Goursat problem and perform numerical computations on a coordinate grid. The process culminates in the creation of a user-friendly prototype simulator that allows users to easily input surface equations and obtain volume estimates.

Figure 1. Research Design

3. FINDINGS

This section outlines the primary results of the project, centred on estimating the volume of Mount Kinabalu through mathematical modelling and numerical methods. The research comprised extracting the mountain's surface equation, transforming it into the Goursat problem format, and employing the forward difference method to solve the equation. Beyond estimating the mountain's volume, the project also resulted in the creation of a prototype simulator aimed at streamlining terrain analysis. The findings below underscore the outcomes of these endeavours.

3.1 Surface Equation

The general surface equation of mountain is given as (Afken, 2005):

$$U(x,y) = t \exp\left(-\frac{x^2+y^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \tag{2}$$

where, t is height, σ is width of the mountain.

Moreover, the surface equation for Mount Kinabalu was successfully derived using data retrieved from <https://www.sabahparks.org/> as follows:

$$U(x, y) = 4095 \exp\left(\frac{-x^2 + y^2}{2(10000)^2}\right). \quad (3)$$

Therefore, the above equation served as the basis for further mathematical modelling.

3.2 Formulate Goursat Problem

The surface equation (3) is extract into the Goursat problem form as (1) will yields

$$\begin{aligned} u_{xy} &= \frac{819}{2(10000)^2} \exp\left(\frac{-x^2 + y^2}{2(10000)^2}\right) \\ u(0, y) &= 4095 \exp\left(\frac{-y^2}{2(10000)^2}\right) \\ u(x, 0) &= 4095 \exp\left(\frac{-x^2}{2(10000)^2}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$0 \leq x \leq 11500, \quad 0 \leq y \leq 11500, \quad \text{step size, } h = 2875.$$

where, domain of x and y is average values of width and length of the mountain, respectively.

This reformulation successfully enabled the effective application of the Goursat initial value conditions, facilitating numerical computation. This significant achievement converted complex surface geometry into a solvable mathematical framework, thereby simplifying the entire approach.

3.3 Implement Numerical Method

The left-hand side of equation (4) will discretise using forward difference method written as:

$$u_{xy} = \frac{1}{h^2} [u(x+h, y+h) - u(x+h, y) - u(x, y+h) + u(x, y)]. \quad (5)$$

The new scheme for extraction Goursat form can be generated by substituting (5) into (4) as

$$\frac{1}{h^2} [u(x+h, y+h) - u(x+h, y) - u(x, y+h) + u(x, y)] = \frac{819}{2(10000)^2} \exp\left(\frac{-x^2 + y^2}{2(10000)^2}\right). \quad (6)$$

The indexing form is given by:

$$u_{i+1, j+1} = u_{i+1, j} + u_{i, j+1} - u_{i, j} + h^2 \left[\frac{819}{2(10000)^2} \exp\left(\frac{-h^2(i-1)^2 + (j-1)^2}{2(10000)^2}\right) \right]. \quad (7)$$

where $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \left(\frac{c}{k} - 1\right)$ and $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \left(\frac{d}{h} - 1\right)$. The parameter c, d, k , and h are the range of x, y , the grid size for the domain x and the grid size for the domain y , respectively.

Therefore, the value of u will be computed using the aid of Maple 18 and MATLAB R2014a software given as:

Table 1. Approximated numerical solution, $u(x, y)$ at $h = 2875$.

(x, y)	0	2875	5750	8625	11500
0	4095	3929.2108	3471.0398	2823.0379	2113.8622
2875	3929.2108	3763.4216	3305.2506	2657.2487	1948.0730
5750	3471.0398	3305.2506	2872.8374	2270.3440	1616.6872
8625	2823.0379	2657.2487	2270.3440	1748.2544	1192.6877
11500	2113.8622	1948.0730	1616.6872	1192.6877	756.7876

Figure 2. Estimated Surface Region of Mount Kinabalu at $h = 2875$

The numerical results in Table 1 and Figure 2 will be used to demonstrate the estimate volume and surface region of Mount Kinabalu.

3.4 Volume Estimation

The formula of estimating the volume using vector as follows (Stewart, 2012):

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Let } a &= \overline{P_1P_2} = P_2 - P_1 \\
 b &= \overline{P_1P_3} = P_3 - P_1 \\
 c &= \text{height} \\
 \therefore V &= 4|c \cdot (a \times b)|
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{8}$$

Based on the approximated numerical solution in Table 1, we can easily get the referred coordinates as

$$\begin{aligned}
 P_1 &= (0, 0, 4095), \\
 P_2 &= (11500, 0, 2113.8622), \\
 P_3 &= (0, 11500, 2113.8622), \\
 c &= (0, 0, 4095).
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{9}$$

Hence, by applying points (9) into volume formula in (8) the estimated volume of Mount Kinabalu is 2,229,618,283,601.16 meter³.

3.5 Prototype Simulator

The prototype simulator to estimate the volume of Mount Kinabalu can be illustrated in the Figure 3 as follows:

The figure shows a web-based prototype simulator interface. It consists of several input fields and buttons arranged vertically. At the top, there is a label 'Insert Surface Equation:' followed by a wide text input field. Below this is a button labeled 'Extract to Goursat Form'. The next section has a label 'Goursat Form (Uxy):' followed by another wide text input field. Below that is a button labeled 'Apply Numerical Method'. This is followed by three separate input fields, each with a label: 'Enter x:', 'Enter y:', and 'Enter h:'. At the bottom of the interface are two more buttons: 'Demonstrate U(x,y)' and 'Calculate Volume'.

Figure 3. Prototype Simulator

4. DISCUSSION

This project aimed to estimate the volume of Mount Kinabalu using numerical methods and vector calculus. By converting the mountain's surface equation into the Goursat problem and applying the forward difference method, we approximated the volume of a section of the mountain. This

estimated volume demonstrates how vector formulas can be utilized for volume estimation. However, it's important to note that this value is derived from a simplified model with specific assumptions, such as the chosen domain and step size.

The prototype simulator developed during this project streamlines the process of calculating surface regions and volumes. It enables users to input surface data and generate volume results efficiently. The visual representation of the mountain's surface adds clarity, while the incorporation of vector-based calculations ensures a mathematically sound approach.

Future research could enhance the prototype simulator with a graphical user interface (GUI), making it even more user-friendly and accessible. This improvement would allow users to interact with the tool more intuitively, boosting its functionality and usability for geographical analysis. Further enhancements could also include more advanced numerical methods to improve the precision of volume estimations for complex terrains.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the estimated volume of Mount Kinabalu is **2,229,618,283,601.16 meter³** demonstrates the feasibility of this method, and with further development, the prototype simulator could become a valuable tool for volume calculations in geographical and scientific applications.

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